

Codebook for the paper “An Investigation of Low-Code Development Adoption in a Finnish Consulting Firm” by Dongmei Gao and Fabian Fagerholm.

1. Codebook

Code	Subcode	Definition
background	personal background	Participants’ previous experience of working with LCDPs and how they got started
	motivation	Motivation of adopting LCDPs, including those of participants, clients, and the LCD team.
	decision-making	Strategies and considerations for deciding on a low-code solution and choosing a platform.
	uncategorized	Others that are related to background information.
work mode	roles and responsibilities	Participants’ roles and responsibilities in working with LCDPs.
	development lifecycle	Typical development life cycle when using LCDP and the phases it includes, such as such as planning, designing, developing, testing, deployment, and maintenance.
	team collaboration	Ways of collaborating with other team members, especially between different roles.
	uncategorized	Others that are related to work mode.
client collaboration	client roles	Roles of people from the client side.
	client collaboration	This can be the description of the target users of LCD in the article, such as non-technical users.
	client knowledge	Skills or knowledge that participants expect clients to have to have a better collaboration.
	client experience	clients’ experience and doubts about low-code solutions.
	challenges	Challenges participants have encountered when collaborating with clients, especially those caused by LCDPs.

	uncategorized	Others that are related to client collaboration.
overall experience	experience	Overall feelings about working with LCDPs, such as interesting and challenging.
	benefits	Benefits of adopting LCDP, including benefits to work and personal development.
	challenges	Challenges participants have encountered when working with LCDPs, especially those caused by LCDPs.
	required competencies	Skills that are important for different roles working with LCDPs.
	personal preference	Participants' personal preference for staying in low-code or specialized code areas.
	future vision of LCD	Participants' personal visions about the future of low-code development.
	future vision of consulting firms	The way forward for the consulting firm, if their vision of low-code development is realized in the future.
	citizen development	Participants' perspectives about citizen development.
	uncategorized	Others that are related to overall experience

2. Coding specimens

Interview snippets	Code
<p>Researcher: How do customers typically become low code customers in your company?</p> <p>Participant: There are two ways. One way is the traditional way, where we [receive a request for a quote]: Can you provide us OutSystem services or Power Platform services?</p> <p>So our customer directly asks us for something, they already have low-code practice there or whatever, and they directly ask for that. But as we know, low-code is still making its way to the general public.</p> <p>So, let's say, and this doesn't happen very often, the [request] comes in and we start responding to it.</p> <p>As often happens we end up in a situation where we hear about the customer or current customer or some kind of public tender comes in</p>	<p>background: motivation: two ways to provide clients with low-code solutions</p> <p>background: motivation: clients directly ask for low-code solutions</p> <p>background: motivation: consulting firm introduce low-code solution based on clients' needs</p>

<p>where they are looking for a product to do something. For example CRM products and then they have a little bit special needs in the environment where they are working or the requirements are a bit special and so on and so forth.</p> <p>So those off-the-shelf stuff is not like spot on, but they need to customize it quite heavily and in those discussions we are promoting ourselves that hey, this is another opportunity.</p> <p>So this tailor-made software is a way which they usually don't prefer in those kinds of cases. These kinds of off-the-shelf things which they need to heavily customize. Then this some of the middle ground maybe is where you have this kind of productized platform – Low-code platform which is designed for customization.</p> <p>And that is like maybe the 2nd way that we bring as we understand the need or the problem of the customer, we introduce a low-code platform as one possible solution for the need and sometimes it's something that our customer sees the value as well and so so.</p>	
<p>Researcher: And how would you say that the low code platform like you use OutSystems, does that play any role in your collaboration?</p> <p>Participant: The thing is well. I think it is easy to go through code together 'cause it is a visual thing. You are sharing a screen and you can see the flow as the code progresses, so it's quite easy to look at the code and say, oh here's the problem, here's the bug. Or maybe that's like, oh, does this process work as it should? Which I think might be a bit more difficult if you are reading traditional code 'cause it's just easier to understand visually I feel.</p> <p>And then of course, like when you are building a UI, it's quite easy to change things while you are working with the other people, like you can just do changes live and you can see how it looks immediately and you can just publish it and test it. All of them are on your own computers 'cause it's a shared environment.</p>	<p>work mode: team collaboration: LCDPs' visual interface helps understand the code</p> <p>work mode: team collaborative mode: easy to make live changes</p> <p>work mode: team collaboration: LCDPs provide a shared environment</p>
<p>Researcher: So if we think of these two projects that you have already had and then maybe the starting of the one that you have begun to build, is it possible to somehow describe the overall life cycle of a low code application by looking at these? What's the starting point? And then how does it go forward and how do you finish?</p> <p>Participant: Yeah, at least at the starting point [is ...].</p> <p>The prototyping is like the thing in the starting point. So we can build proof of concept, especially when we have for example data laying somewhere outside a data warehouse or we need integration, for example those performance issues might be something that we</p>	<p>work mode: development lifecycle: proof-of-concept is created as a starting point</p>

<p>come up with, so we need to check something on that side, but also when we have the low-code power platform solutions are new to the customers, so to make everybody also our developers feel comfortable and confident. Because it's fast to build a Proof of concepts or prototype, that may differ from the traditional software projects. So I think that's the starting point.</p>	
<p>Researcher: And you mentioned the communication is very similar to other projects and you also mentioned low code gives you a lot of possibilities to do almost everything. I still want to ask, are there any challenges with customer communication and collaboration related to low code?</p> <p>Participant: Yeah, there's one thing which is that they have to pay a lot of licenses for OutSystems. And also they cannot ask everything from us, but there are some questions they have to ask from OutSystems and they haven't got responses to their mails and it's kind of like for example security, like cybersecurity. It's kind of like they have to deal with both us and OutSystems. So it's a bit divided. That would be perhaps easier for them if we would be kind of taking care of everything and also the maintenance is like. What is our role in maintenance and what is OutSystems'? It is kind of a bit complicated for them.</p>	<p>client collaboration: challenges: pay a lot for licenses</p> <p>client collaboration: challenges: it is complicated to deal .with both parties since responsibilities are divided.</p>
<p>Researcher: So what do you think of the future of low-code technology? So where is it going from your perspective?</p> <p>Participant: It's gonna be bigger. It's gonna take some space on the pro-coding now when we have this kind of generative AI. Also in the power platform we can use Co-pilot and ChatGPT under the hood. So it's gonna be like that. That's gonna be a big change coming. And it's gonna grow very fast. A lot. Next three years. I would say that's took lots of space for the pro-coders and I think a big company that's gonna be there if they're doing the pro-code consulting and pro-code development, there's gonna be maybe some chasing those people moving in this field. I think so. And, it's good to work with low-code. There's gonna be jobs available.</p>	<p>Overall experience: future vision of LCD: LCD will take some space from pro-code.</p> <p>future vision of LCD: AI will be integrated into LCD</p> <p>future vision of LCD: more people will transition to the LCD field.</p> <p>future vision of LCD: more jobs will be available</p>